

Black Semiconductor pioneers integrated graphene photonics to revolutionise chip-to-chip communication

Best practice category	Strengthening research & design capabilities; Partner collaboration and open ecosystems; Scaling innovative chip technologies
Stakeholder group	Startups and research-driven companies
Value chain position	R&D, Chip Design, Fabrication

General Information

Black Semiconductor GmbH, is a fast growing startup based in **Aachen, Germany**. The company combines photonics and electronics on a single wafer through the use of an innovative material: graphene. Its technology helps chip-to-chip optical connections, allowing multiple chips to communicate almost as if they were a single system, with significant benefits in terms of performance, energy efficiency and reduced production costs. Founded in 2020, Black Semiconductor has rapidly scaled its growth: in just a few years, it has raised public and private funds, €11.2M in VC, including public funding, developed wafer manufacturing technology, and, as early as 2025, began construction of its scalable pilot line for 300mm wafers in the 15,000m² FabOne.

Activities and best practices

- The startup develops **integrated electronic-photonic circuits (IGP)** that enable optical communication between chips using graphene. This technology increases data transmission speed and reduces energy consumption. Black Semiconductor has launched FabONE, set to become the world's first production facility for graphene-based optical chips on 300 mm wafers. Factory construction is done in partnership with Exyte, a global leader in semiconductor engineering and factory construction, ensuring industry standards of excellence and rigorous timelines. FabONE combines production and office space, enabling the creation of a scalable pilot line and accelerating the transition from industrial research to the production of energy-efficient, high-performance chips, with applications in **AI, HPC, 5G, and autonomous driving**.
- Black Semiconductor also collaborates with partners such as Critical Manufacturing for the fab automation systems, as well as integrating the know-how of Applied Nanolayers to accelerate the development of materials and processes. It participates in strategic European projects such as IPCEI, contributing to European technological sovereignty; and in Horizon Europe projects including 2DNeuralVision, a Graphene Flagship project focused on low-power computer vision systems based on graphene and other 2D materials.

Through these activities, Black Semiconductor works closely with high-level industrial partners, universities and research centres to support skills development and strengthen the European microelectronics and photonics ecosystem. It was Awarded with the SPARK Award, which rewards disruptive innovation with sound science and clear practical relevance, assessing innovation quality, scalability and potential for lasting impact, and it was a finalist of the Deutscher Gründerpreis 2025, one of the most respected awards in Germany for entrepreneurship, which selects companies par excellence in technology, innovation, long-term vision, and contribution to the German innovation ecosystem.

Challenges addressed with this practice

Black Semiconductor addresses central challenges for the European semiconductor ecosystem, in particular the bottleneck of inter-chip communication, the shift from research to industrial manufacturing and the scalability of technologies based on new materials, while promoting new approaches to computing architectures. Through the development of Integrated Graphene Photonics (IGP) and the implementation of FabONE, the startup bridges the gap between laboratory and industrial-scale manufacturing prototypes, making the integration of photonics and electronics compatible with CMOS processes. Participation in strategic European initiatives and industrial partnerships also underline the importance of connectivity within the ecosystem, helping to strengthen technological sovereignty and European competitiveness in advanced semiconductors.